

Innovative Sustainable Solar Photovoltaic Insect Trap of Double Catching Mechanisms for Insect Monitoring

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Abstract: This innovation achieves the design, implementation, and testing of a solar photovoltaic insect trap of double catching mechanisms either by sticking to yellow colored cardboard or by falling into a pan with water. The results of the performance of the trap revealed that the trap attracted and caught seven different insect genera for 13 days of operation in a plastic house planted with eggplant. Only the whitefly (*Trialeurodes vaporariorum*) and leaf miner (*Liriomyza sativae*) among the scouted genera were recorded as pests on eggplant with total numbers of 363 and 103 adults, respectively. The trap is durable, easily carried, and manufactured.

Keywords: Insect trap, Light trap, Renewable energy, Insect pests, Physical insect control

Insects are widespread organisms in nature and are among the important pests that cause severe damage to crops and threaten global food security (Culliney 2014, Pimentel 2017). Also, other insect species parasitize humans and animals; transmit several epidemic diseases, and bothering human lives. Human has struggled to control insect pests since the prehistoric times to minimize their damage. Various methods were innovated to control insect pests as chemical (i. e. insecticides), biological (i. e. natural pathogens, predators, and parasites) and physical methods (i.e. traps, nets, heat, and light). Various insect traps were innovated (light, colored, pheromone, and food (kairomones) and become an important component of the integrated insect management programs (Horowitz and Isaac 2004, United States Patent Application Publication 2008, Ahmad and Norman 2011, Al-Deeb et al 2012, Atakan and Serkan 2015). Renewable energy research, especially solar energy has received worldwide attention. Agriculture is not in isolation from solar energy applications. Solar energy is used to provide villages with electricity for lighting and heating, running water pumps, operating food factories and cold stores, etc. (Ali et al 2012, Torhizi et al 2017). Having a chance to replace the common light insect trap with solar photovoltaic will be of great deal importance to avoid some of the defects and hazards that accompany with the regular electrical traps, to contribute to the programs of integrated management of many insect pests and to evaluate the effectiveness of different control methods.

This study reports on the design, implementation, and performance of a sustainable and eco-friendly, solar photovoltaic trap with double attraction and catching mechanisms for insect monitoring.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The theoretical view of the targeted trap: The trap is designed to have double mechanisms of insect attractions and double caught mechanisms. It can work at day and night times in open and protected fields. The double attractions mechanism relies on solar energy as a source of light and yellow cardboard.

Trap components: The trap model was manufactured in the light of a schematic diagram in which the theoretical view of the target trap was developed (Fig. 1A). It consists of:

1. A metal structure that is locally designed to combine trap components.
2. Solar panels generate electrical energy from the sun (18V-10W) (Fig. 1B).
3. Rechargeable battery (12V-7AH) (Fig. 1B).
4. A light source consisting of an economical, low-power LED lamp 3W.
5. Adhesive yellow-colored or insect pheromone impregnated cardboard.
6. A plastic pan.

Trap working mechanisms: During the daylight hours, the solar panel converts the sunlight into electrical energy and stores it in the rechargeable battery. At night hours the LED lamp will be on to give bright light, which attracts insects of night flying habit. The attracted insects begin with the rotating movement around the lamp, and during this movement, the trap catches insects with one of two mechanisms, either by sticking to the yellow-colored cardboards or by falling into the plastic bucket containing water. During the day hours, however, insect pests are attracted to the yellow-colored or pheromone embedded cardboard as profusely reported in the literature (Atakan and Ramazan 2004, Wallis and Shaw

2008, Ahmad et al 2011, Al-Deeb et al 2012, Atakan and Serkan 2015). In light of the schematic layout design model, the metal frame was fabricated locally and provided with an imported solar panel. The trap parts were linked or assembled and ready to operate after the solar panel charged the battery and the trap was provided with yellow-colored cardboards (Fig. 2A). The trap operated at night (Fig. 2B).

The performance of the trap was evaluated by placing the trap inside a plastic house of the Experimental Station of the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Anbar (Fig. 5A). The house was planted with eggplant. Data were gathered as insect scouting (numbers and types) that stuck to the cardboard or fell into the water in the pan at the midday every 3 days in a row for 13 days (1-13 April 2019). After each reading, both the cardboard and the water in the pan were replaced.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the trap performance revealed that the trap attracted and caught several different insect species existed in the plastic house-grown with the eggplant (Fig. 5B).

The types of insects were monitored by their attraction to the two methods of trapping that characterize the trap, either by sticking to the yellow cardboard or falling into the water during their attraction to the light and its rotation movement around it. Seven different genera belong to different insect families were recorded. The genus detected was topped with two main pests of eggplant (whitefly and leaf miner) (Table 1).

The total number of the whitefly was 363 and the leaf miner was 105 for the period 1-13 April. As for the rest of the species that were caught none included in the list of eggplant pests. The highest scouted number, 310 insects were of the non-biting midges and the rest of was a butterfly, mosquitoes, and houseflies ranged between 1-22 insects for this period. Besides, only one adult of insect natural enemy (green lacewings (*Chrysopa* spp)) was among the none pests caught. It is striking that the detected whitefly was caught in the trap by both by falling into the water pan and sticking to the yellow cardboard, while the leaf miner adults were confined to the adhesive yellow cardboard. This finding is most probably attributes to the behavior of each genus (Owens and Lewis 2018). This solar-powered photovoltaic trap was developed in this study to avoid some of the defects and electrical hazards that accompany the regular photovoltaic traps. The trap is a useful and crucial component in the programs of integrated management of many insect pests as previously recommended (Wallis and Shaw 2008, Ahmad et al 2011, Al-Deeb et al 2012, Zgaib et al 2016). The

Fig. 1. A: The trap schematic diagram; B: The solar unit parts, solar panel, LED lamp, and rechargeable battery

Fig. 2A. The trap after assembly; B: The trap operated at night

Fig. 3. A: The trap in greenhouse; B: A sample of the trap performance

Table 1. Numbers and species of insects caught by the trap from the plastic house-grown with eggplant

Insect	Total	Catching device							
		Adhesive card				Water pan			
		Reading date at 12 pm							
		4 Apr	7 Apr	10 Apr	13 Apr	4 Apr	7 Apr	10 Apr	13 Apr
Whitefly <i>Trialeurodes vaporariorum</i>	363	60	68	42	56	27	33	41	36
Leaf Minor <i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	105	39	28	21	17	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Non- Biting Medage <i>Chironomidis</i> spp.	310	77	63	50	30	18	27	39	14
Mosquito spp.	22	0.0	7	3	12	3	0.0	0.0	0.0
Housefly <i>Musca domestica</i>	19	4	5	9	0.0	0.0	1	0.0	0.0
Monarch Butterfly <i>Danaus</i> spp.	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Green lacewings <i>Chrysopa</i> spp.	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

trap can be applied to perform many important functions, including determining the activity periods and density for each species of insect pests, making a decision for appropriate times to use pesticides according to their economic threshold, and collecting certain insect species to eliminate and prevent them from breeding and spreading.

CONCLUSION

This trap was developed to avoid some of the defects and electrical hazards that accompany with the regular electrical traps, to contribute to the programs of integrated management of many insect pests and to evaluate the effectiveness of different control methods. It is sustained and continues working during the hours of the day and night, safe and ecofriendly. It combines two mechanisms for catching insects at the same time. Furthermore, it enables to direct its action against certain insect species by using insect pheromone or colored light or cardboard, simple manufacturing, easy to apply, and cheap.

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